

Comment on “What is quantum biology?”

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In their Perspective [1], Scholes and Fleming present an account that is epistemologically inconsistent and risks conveying a misleading view of quantum biology.

While the authors caution against speculative claims of quantum biological effects, this standard is not applied consistently. For instance, they assert that “*evolution has tweaked the local protein environments of the chromophores to set up these resonances*”. Definitive claims about what evolution has specifically optimized over billions of years in such highly complex, multilevel systems, where multiscale quantum and classical processes coexist, cannot be rigorously substantiated. Thus, while the authors implicitly invoke a standard of rigor that serves to exclude recent, grounded work on testable quantum effects (see below), they simultaneously express striking certainty about a highly specific evolutionary outcome.

The historical trajectory of quantum effects in photosynthesis further exposes this inconsistency. Oscillatory signals once interpreted as evidence of long-lived quantum coherence in energy transport are now understood as signatures of classical vibrational coherence. This shift is not a minor technical correction but a prolonged episode of overinterpretation. This is not a critique of the early studies, which were inspiring and advanced new experimental directions. However, the authors in [1] sidestep this history, obscuring a central lesson that directly bears on the standards they advocate.

Similarly, the authors leap from observations of neural activity to claims about empathy and mother-infant interaction. Extrapolations of neural synchronization to explanations for complex social phenomena risk crossing the boundary from scientific reasoning into pseudoscientific speculation. Likewise, the authors reiterate Orch-OR-type ideas that attempted to amalgamate several poorly understood domains, such as gravity, quantum physics of complex systems, and consciousness, under the expectation that their synthesis yields greater explanatory clarity, yet this reiteration does not currently contribute to rigorous, experimentally grounded progress in modern quantum biology.

By contrast, the account of the Radical-Pair Mechanism (RPM) of magnetoreception is notably unrepresentative. RPM has arguably emerged as the cleanest paradigm of quantum biology, mainly due to the relatively weak environmental coupling of electronic and nuclear spins. Yet the authors in [1] omit work that addresses the central challenge they themselves empha-

size: the unambiguous detection of quantum coherence in living systems. Theoretical developments have unraveled the fundamental role of quantum measurements in RPM, linking molecular-level quantum processes to measurable biochemical kinetics, including manifestations of the Quantum Zeno Effect [2, 3], and connecting to experimentally accessible relaxation rates [4]. More recent work connected quantifiers of quantum coherence [5] with physiological observables [6], while biophysical experiments identified magnetic structures that may further illuminate these mechanisms [7].

Taken together, these issues reveal a systematic asymmetry in standards of evidence undermining the stated call for epistemic rigor. While urging epistemological scrutiny, the authors’ narrative selectively amplifies claims and interpretations of an exceedingly speculative nature, downplays substantive revisions of earlier claims, and overlooks concrete progress where experimentally tractable and conceptually clean mechanisms provide a methodologically robust route toward validation. The result is a perspective that risks perpetuating a distorted view of the achievements and future prospects of quantum biology.

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